

Methodology Guide for Task 3.2

(Systems mapping and transformative interventions)

CzechGlobe

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WORKSHOP 1: SYSTEMS MAPPING

WHAT WILL BE DONE

Case coordinators/workshop facilitators with the learning communities will collaboratively develop a systems map (using a native language) which will be visualized in a form of onion diagram (= a chart that helps to visualise the different system layers and their relationships).

1-1.5 hour

GOAL

Main aim is **to map the system of your case study**. This means to identify the **main factors (or other systems)** influencing the key system and to organize them according to the degree of influence. (Optional: to identify key relationships – negative, positive - between these factors)

OUTPUT

A systems map in the form of an **onion diagram with 3 circles:**

- **the core circle: your case study**

- **second + third circles:** factors influencing your case study which is at the core (based on level of influence)

→ **second circle: direct factors** (e.g. these have direct influence on your case, such as local community-level factors, local policy or economic drivers etc.)

→ **third circle: distal factors** (e.g. these have indirect effect, these broader drivers such as socioeconomic drivers, demographic, or factors at national level)

TOOLS NEEDED

- a **template of an onion diagram (A1 format ideally)** that will be used for mapping (can be drawn by hand on a large format paper)
- **post-it notes and markers of different colours**
- **a short ppt on systems mapping** (can be downloaded [here](#))

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Systems mapping is a process of visual depiction of a particular system in order to provide a simplified understanding of system and to visualize the relationships among its component (e.g., actors, flows, ...). The onion metaphor is used in systems mapping to imagine systems in a way that they are split into layers, which makes it easier to think about and understand its different parts and relationships.

In WS 1 we will be using an onion diagram with 3 circles (layers), which will contain one inner circle, representing **the core concept (= your case study)**, and two circles (layers) that

surround the core concept. You with your learning communities will together identify **the most important factors influencing your core concept (case study)** and place them into these two circles **according to the degree of influence: direct factors** (e.g. community-level factors or other direct drivers) will be placed in **second circle**, **distal factors** (e.g. national-level factors or other indirect drivers) will be placed in the **third circle** (see figure below).

Further reading:

Yanniek Schoonhoven & Hens Runhaar (2018) Conditions for the adoption of agro-ecological farming practices: a holistic framework illustrated with the case of almond farming in Andalusia, *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, 16:6, 442-454, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14735903.2018.1537664>

Leventon, J., Buhr, M., Kessler, L. et al. Processes of sustainability transformation across systems scales: leveraging systemic change in the textile sector. *Sustain Sci* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-023-01436-8>

Example of onion model (based on Leventon et al. 2023):

In this onion model there is a visualisation of the production system of textile sector in Germany (= core system, in the centre) and the most important factors (systems) influencing this system.

Examples of factors (based on Schoonhoven and Runhaar 2018):

Economic	Economic system (wholesalers, retailers, consumers)
	Cost-benefit ratio
	Subsidies
	Finance and investment
	Market
	Demand
	...
Social	Values (cultural, religious, ...)
	Social norms
	Education
	Gender
	Community support
	Public opinion
	..
Political	Political system
	Legislation, policy and regulations
	Support from government
	Spatial planning
	...
Other	Species conservation
	Monitoring and awareness
	Food production
	Tourism
	Land-use changes

	Resources overexploitation
	Innovativeness
	Communication
	Skills
	Responsibility for future generations
	Unsustainable behaviour
	...

INSTRUCTIONS

1. Introduction (5 mins): allow participant to introduce themselves if they are unacquainted, make a quick ice-breaker activity (optional).

2. Set context for the systems mapping exercise (5 mins)

Explain to the participants what will be done - see section Theoretical background above + you can display ppt slide made by CzechGlobe (can be downloaded [here](#))

You can ask your participants these questions:

What is the core concept in your case study? (This should be the key idea of your case study – e.g. Local food production and biodiversity conservation, Engagement of migrants, Strengthening nature connectedness, etc ...)

3. Identify key factors (20 mins)

Encourage your participants to brainstorm what factors they think influence the core concept/key idea - either directly or indirectly. They ideally write these factors down on a post-it notes so it is possible to move these across layers as the discussion develops, or directly into layers of onion. Each post-it should represent only one factor. Populate the layers as accurately as possible.

4. Check the systems map (10 mins)

Ask your participants to check and reflect the map (onion diagram) after it is completed. If some factors are very similar or represent the same thing, try to cluster them.

OPTIONAL: 5. Identify key relationships between factors (20-30 mins)

In case there is time, participants can describe how the components (factors and core concept) in onion model influence each other. Participants (or you – facilitators, according to the participants' instructions) mark *influence arrows* into the onion model.

Examples of guiding questions you can ask participants:

Where in the system are the flows of knowledge, information, influence, money, people? Which components are related to which other components in the system? How are the components interrelated? Do they influence each other either positively (+) or negatively (-)? Are there any outside influences that shape the system?

REPORTING REQUEST

After the workshop, please, **translate the onion diagram** into English and send it to the CzechGlobe team (louckova.b@czechlobe.cz) Also please provide a **brief audio or video description of your onion diagram in English**. Lastly, please do not forget to take pictures during the workshop!

NOTES:

WORKSHOP 2: LEVERAGE POINTS

WHAT WILL BE DONE

*Participants will use their systems maps from WS1, combined with selected interventions being trialled in the P4B project. Using a Leverage Points framework, they will identify which systems properties are targeted by the interventions and will create **a narrative of how that change happens (the narrative of change)**.*

Through the workshop, one or few interventions (the levers) will be chosen to explore which layers of the system they target. You will be then asked to consider how these interventions could lever changes through the materials, processes, design and intent of those systems and in what order.

Key questions:

1. What intervention(s) do you identify in your case?
2. Where in your system map (WS1) do they intervene? (I.e., In which layer of your onion diagram)?
3. How does the intervention target the leverage points (materials, processes, design, intent)?

1 - 1.5 hours

GOAL

To outline narratives of change as to how specific interventions create change, in which layer of the system, through which leverage points may interventions create desired systems transformation.

OUTPUT

A narrative of change

TOOLS NEEDED

- **systems map** that was developed in WS1
- **A4 papers**
- **Pens and markers**
- **a short ppt on leverage points** (can be downloaded [here](#))

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Leverage points framework

Systems are interconnected networks of actors and organisations, connected via flows of materials, information and power. Within a system thinking perspective, we can understand systems to have properties of *materials*, *processes*, *design* and *paradigms*. These properties are leverage points at which we can intervene to change the system towards more sustainable outcomes.

We use the following four categories that characterise leverage points: 1) *materials* 2) *processes* 3) *design* and 4) *intent*. Starting from the deepest, *intent* relates to the worldviews and paradigms that are being embodied and enacted by the system. *Design* refers to the structures, actors and organisations in the system and how they interact with each other. *Processes* refer to the feedbacks or procedures that move materials around the system, and *materials* are the flows of matters within the system, such as money or fabrics and other resources.

The Leverage Points framework says that a change can be created in a system by targeting leverage Points. Shallower leverage points are usually easier to see and create change, but they do not change the system very far initially. Deeper leverage points are harder to see, but will create more fundamental change. They do so because changing e.g. *intent* necessarily requires change in all the shallower leverage points.

Further reading:

Abson DJ, Fischer J, Leventon J, Newig J, Schomerus T, Vilsmaier U, von Wehrden H, Abernethy P, Ives CD, Jager NW, Lang DJ, (2017) Leverage points for sustainability transformation. *AMBIO* 46 (1):30–39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-016-0800-y>

Fischer J, Riechers M (2019) A leverage points perspective on sustainability. *People Nat* 1 (1):115–120. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.13>

Leventon, J., Buhr, M., Kessler, L. et al. Processes of sustainability transformation across systems scales: leveraging systemic change in the textile sector. *Sustain Sci* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-023-01436-8> (examples of interventions targeting specific leverage points)

Examples of leverage points (from Fischer and Riechers 2019):

Leverage points:		Example:
Material	Constants, parameters, numbers	Average fuel consumption of a car
	Size of buffer stocks, relative to flows	Amount of total standing timber in a production forest
	Structure of material stocks and flows	Run-off dynamics of nutrients from agricultural fields into adjacent water bodies
Processes	Length of delays, relative to rate of system change	Time it takes for the ozone hole to close after harmful emissions cease
	Strength of negative feedback loops	The extent to which a lake can absorb nutrients and thus remain clear
	Gain around positive feedback loops	The extent to which poverty leads to population growth, which may further exacerbate poverty
Design	Structure of information flows	Consumer knowledge about where certain products come from
	Rules of the system (incentives, constraints) Power to change system structure or self-organize	Policies governing natural resources, including among others taxes and regulations Ability of farmers to organize the sustainable use of a communal pasture
Intent	Goals of the system	Organization of global institutions to support free trade versus global equity
	Paradigm underpinning the system	A 'green revolution' paradigm underpinning agricultural policies
	Power to transcend paradigms	The conscious shift from a growth-based economy growth to a steady-state economy

INSTRUCTIONS FOR FACILITATORS

1. Present the systems map that was developed during WS1 (a quick recap) (5-10 mins)

2. Set context for the LP framework (10 mins)

Explain to the participants what will be done. Present the outline of Leverage Points (see section **Theoretical background above**) + you can also use the ppt slides provided by CzechGlobe (can be download [here](#))

3. Ask the group to select the intervention(s) they would like to explore in depth as first. These can be interventions they are already trialing, or interventions selected from the P4B directory of methods. They should select 1 most important intervention to start with, and maximum 2 other interventions (5 mins).

4. For the first intervention, ask the group to discuss and write on an A4 paper (in big letters): i) who instigates the intervention, and ii) who participates in the intervention. Encourage your participants to write notes in a way that you can easily translate to English – e.g. notes/bullet points not a long text (5-10 mins).

5. Provide the group with 4 pieces of A4 paper – each piece should be labelled as one of the leverage points (materials, processes, design, intent). Ask participants to complete an A4 sheet for each of the 4 leverage points, exploring **how the intervention would target each** (Perhaps some leverage points are not included if the group feels they aren't targeted by the intervention). **Write the name of the intervention on the bottom right** of each paper (20 minutes).

Example:

<p>Materials:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p><i>Intervention</i></p>	<p>Processes:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p><i>Intervention</i></p>	<p>Design:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p><i>Intervention</i></p>	<p>Intent:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p><i>Intervention</i></p>
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6. Participants then put the identified Leverage Points on the table/wall, in the order in which the change take place, to describe their narrative of change (next step). (5 minutes)

7. A final A4 paper will be added at the end of this 'leverage points path' to describe the narrative of change. This means to **characterise the change that has occurred** as a result of the intervention (as described in the LPs). (5 minutes).

8. Briefly repeat steps 4, 5 and 6 for each of selected interventions. Make sure the name of the intervention is always included on the bottom right of each LP so we don't loose track (20 mins).

9. Voice record this step to help your write-up! To conclude and debrief the workshop, the facilitator should summarise the narratives of change that the participants have created, allowing participants to correct interpretations. (10 mins)

(DETAILED INSTRUCTIONS FOR PARTICIPANTS)

1. For your chosen intervention, write in big letters on an A4 paper, which system layer it intervenes in, who should instigate the intervention, and who should participate in the intervention. Put this on the left-hand side of your table.
2. Discuss, and fill out how the intervention targets the 4 leverage points. Try to keep it specific to the system layer you are targeting, and the people participating. It is ok to decide that some LPs are not changed.
3. Arrange the leverage points in the order to which they change, next to your intervention paper (left to right) – e.g. does the intervention target materials first, and then shift structures? Try to narrate the change across LPs.
4. What does the system look like after the intervention has been done? Summarise the change on a final piece of paper, and put it at the end of your LPs. Collectively, you now have a narrative of change for your chosen intervention.
5. Select other 2-3 interventions that might be useful for intervening.
6. Briefly repeat steps 1, 2 and 3 for each of these interventions. If you have time, you might want to explore how the different interventions interact with each other through the leverage points. Play around with the leverage points papers to map that change process.

REPORTING REQUEST

After the workshop, please, **translate the A4 papers into English and summarise them in a document, in the order they were written** (e.g. from left to right on intervention 1, then down to desired system, then left to right on next selected interventions). Send a picture of them to the CzechGlobe team (louckova.b@czechglobe.cz) Also please provide **a brief audio or video description of your narrative of change in English** and send it to the CzechGlobe team.

NOTES:

WORKSHOP 3: MONITORING AND INDICATORS

WHAT WILL BE DONE

Participants will use their systems maps from WS1 and theory of change from WS 2 to create a monitoring strategy and identify indicators of change.

1-1.5 hour

GOAL

To identify a list of indicators of change which will be used to measure success or impacts of interventions implemented and monitor desired changes in the system after the project has run its course.

OUTPUT

A list of indicators and their characteristics (how they will be measured, their purpose, ...)

TOOLS NEEDED

- **A system onion diagram** created in workshop 1
- **A narrative of change** created in workshop 2
- **Flipchart or whiteboard and markers**
- **A4 papers**
- **Pens**
- **A short ppt on monitoring and indicators** (can be downloaded [here](#))

INSTRUCTIONS FOR FACILITATORS

1. Introduce yourself and rationale behind the workshop (*why are we here?*). You can engage participants in a quick ice-breaker activity. (10 mins)

2. Briefly recap and remind participants of system onion diagram created in workshop 1 and summary of narratives of change outlined in workshop 2 to set context for the day's activity. (10 mins)

3. Present indicators and monitoring concepts to participants using the slides provided. (10 mins)

4. Provide the group with a template of the narratives of change created in WS2 and an A4 paper and ask them to discuss and choose one specific change from the template to start with. (10 mins)

5. Ask participants to clearly write the change on the top part of the A4 paper and to **discuss and write all the indicators of change** (quantitative or qualitative metric) they will use to measure this change (*example of indicator: percentage increase in ethnic minority communities engaging with nature and the outdoors*). (10 mins)

6. Ask participants to discuss and write the purpose (what is it for) of the chosen indicators and why they are needed and useful. Encourage participants to write notes/ bullet points that you can easily translate to English. (10 mins)

7. Ask participants to discuss and write how data will be collected to measure the chosen indicators for the change selected (*example: survey, interviews, focus groups*) and how frequently data would be collected (*for example quarterly, annually, bi-annually*). (10 mins)

8. Coffee break (10 mins)

9. Return to the systems map from WS1. Ask participants to discuss and write potential obstacles or problems from the system they are intervening that may have an impact on the use of the indicator or on the accuracy or validity of its findings. (10 mins)

10. Ask participants to return to the template of narratives of change and choose another change they desire to see. Briefly repeat 6,7, 8 and 10. (20 mins)

11. To conclude and debrief the workshop, the facilitator should read out the list of indicators selected and decide together with participants if each indicator meets the checklist of a good indicator as described in the last ppt slide provided. Allow participants to make any additional inputs or changes (15 mins)

REPORTING REQUEST

After the workshop, please, **translate your A4 papers** into English and send them to the CzechGlobe team (louckova.b@czechlobe.cz). Lastly, please do not forget to take pictures during the workshop!

NOTES:

WORKSHOP 4: BARRIERS & OPPORTUNITIES FOR BROADER CHANGE

WHAT WILL BE DONE

Identifying broader impact means that we need to look at the potential effects of interventions that go beyond the boundaries of the initial systems where we expect change to take place. Suggest what opportunities and what barriers do you see in respect to potential broader changes that arise from the interventions in your systems map.

1.5 hours

GOAL

To think about ways to increase the impact of proposed interventions that were implemented through specific leverage points (i.e. the system properties, see results of WS2) in the identified systems in your local case (i.e. the onion diagram, result of WS1).

OUTPUT

Building on the onion diagram from WS1, WS4 will generate an extended system map that shows potential broader impact of the intervention(s) in your case study, either by using post-its (directly in the onion diagram) or A4 papers. The description will include what the broader impact is, how it manifests, and what the opportunities and barriers are.

TOOLS NEEDED

- **Post-it notes** in multiple colours
- **Pens or pencils** (ideally 1 per participant), **Markers** (multiple colours; at least black, blue, red and green)
- **A set of A4 sheets** – for participants so they can make notes, and for final summary per broader impact, opportunity, and barrier.
- **Flipchart**
- **A short ppt on barriers and opportunities for broader impact** (can be downloaded [here](#))

INSTRUCTIONS FOR FACILITATORS

1. Read aloud the goals of the ‘Broader impact’ exercise and revisit the system map (onion diagram created in WS1) and **leverage points** including the narratives of change (from WS2) and place them in a way that everyone can see these

2. Show the example in provided ppt slides for a better idea of this exercise.

3. Pick the first intervention (from WS1 and WS2) and write it down on a post-it note and place the post-it note in your system map in the respective system layer (in case that intervention has been removed after WS1). Now it's time to explore potential broader impacts and the related opportunities and barriers. Ask the following questions one by one to execute the exercise:

a. How would you describe potential broader impacts in your case? Identify all relevant impacts that may occur and write them down on e.g. yellow post-its ; place them on a relevant spot in the system map. Write down a more detailed description on an A4 paper if relevant (or let participants to do so).

b. Which other systems, who or what are potentially affected by the intervention applied in the initial system? Here you will tap on "neighbouring" or related systems to extend the initial system map from WS1 (onion diagram). Identify all relevant systems and write them down on e.g. blue post-its; place them on a relevant spot in the system map. Write down a more detailed description on an A4 paper if relevant. (or let participants to do so).

c. Which factors, actors, or processes enable broader impact? Here you will identify **opportunities** linked to your interventions and initial systems. Identify all relevant opportunities and write them down on e.g. green s post-its; place them on a relevant spot in the system map. Write down a more detailed description on an A4 paper if relevant. (or let participants to do so).

d. Which factors, actors, or processes halt broader change? Here you will identify **barriers** linked to your interventions and initial systems. Identify all relevant barriers and write them down on e.g. pink post-its; place them on a relevant spot in the system map. Write down a more detailed description on an A4 paper if relevant. (or let participants to do so).

4. Pick another intervention (from WS2) in a particular system (WS1) and write the information down on a post-it note. Continue the exercise in a suit described in the 3rd point. Repeat this with maximum 3 most important interventions

5. Finally, once you exploit all interventions in your case, **debrief and discuss results with the group**. Is there anything to add regarding the broader impacts, barriers and opportunities? If several opportunities and barriers per interventions were identified, please highlight the most prominent ones. You can ask any other question that arises from the workshop.

REPORTING REQUEST

After the workshop, **please translate post-it notes and the descriptions (A4 papers) into English and summarize them in a word document**, e.g. in the order they were written or otherwise so we are able to identify their place in the template.

Make a short video, in English, to briefly summarize the information in the template and on the A4 papers.

Send document and video to the CzechGlobe team (louckova.b@czechglobe.cz)

NOTES: